

TO STUDY ABOUT THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INDUCTION PROGRAM**Ajith N¹, Muthumani S², Bethel Erastus-Obilo³**¹MBA Student, Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India²Professor And Head MBA, Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India³Vice President of Academic Affairs & Professor of Criminal Justice, University of Atlanta, Atlanta, GA**ABSTRACT:**

Induction is the process by which new employees are integrated into an organization so that they become productive as soon as possible. In order to ensure that this happens quickly and effectively, the process needs to be planned, managed and adopted into the organization's overall training plans. Orientation or Induction is the first important step in the process of human resource management. It involves familiarization of the newly appointed employees to the work environment of the organization as well as to the fellow employees. This project titled "To study about the effectiveness of the induction program" aims to understand the importance and the effectiveness of the induction process in Sree designs. Through this project, the researcher wants to analyze the opinion of the employees about the induction programme conducted in Sree designs. This study also helps to determine the relationship between the induction input and opinion about the employee output. Responses are collected through questionnaire for this project. A Sample of 110 employees has been chosen for this study. Simple percentage analysis, one way Anova, T-test, weighted average, Chi-square test and correlation analysis are used to analyze this project statistically. We recommend that employee induction should last more than one day, usually 2-5 days.

INTRODUCTION

Recruitment and Training are a noteworthy cost to any association. Bosses along these lines need to boost staff maintenance to guarantee that this project isn't squandered. The underlying impression of an Organization on a worker more often than not remains with them, and it is consequently critical to make this experience a positive one. The New individuals from staff need fundamental data about their terms and state of business, quick workplace. Individuals whatever their industry or calling, need to know how they fit into the association as entire and how their function identifies with that of other individuals and different offices. Normally they additionally need to meet their associates and line chiefs. Every one of these things ought to be canvassed in an Induction Scheme. In any case, very regularly there is no formalized framework for guaranteeing that this happens. Recruits people are left to 'lift things up as they come' or gone up against the conventional handshake visit. This is basically requesting that the new worker embrace an unconcerned state of mind towards the association, accordingly lessening the odds of that representative remaining sufficiently long to contribute their maximum capacity. Work turnover cost cash as well. What's more it uncovers an inadmissible wastage of an association's HR; the most profitable resources it has. Enlistment Program helps with diminishing work turnover by incorporating new representatives adequately into the association.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Organizations put a considerable measure on their workers as far as enlistment and preparing, creating, keeping up and holding them in their association. In spite of the fact that, there is no standard structure for understanding the representatives fulfillment and preparing need process as entire, an extensive variety of elements have been discovered helpful in deciphering worker enlistment program in the association. Kevin et al. (2004). Workforce improvement, the association's achievement in advancing the execution of the representatives by building up fundamental procedures for completing work, giving great working conditions, setting up responsibility and settling on great enlisting decisions

would hold workers in their association. The significance of increasing better comprehension of the variables identified with enlistment, inspiration and maintenance of representatives depends on the Induction program for the association. (Badawy, 1988; Basta and Johnson, 1989; Garden, 1989; Parden, 1981; Sherman, 1986). Satisfaction speaks to a viable reaction to particular parts of the activity or vocation and means the pleasurable or positive passionate state for the representatives working in the association coming about because of an enlistment preparing project of one's activity or profession (Locke, 1976; Porter et al., 1974; Williams and Hazer, 1986).

METHODOLOGY

The primary objective is collected by providing questionnaires to friends, relatives, and colleagues, through emails, WhatsApp, etc. The secondary objective is collected by analyzing websites, vlogs, etc. Advertising can be in any form video, posters, posts, reels, etc., you will get to know about the users and gain the right information that is shared by the social media platform. This research intended to describe and analyze user perception and information that are shared by induction program advertisements. A descriptive research design is used in the study. Descriptive research includes surveys, findings, and enquiries Probability sampling is a technique in which the researcher chooses samples from a larger population using a method based on probability theory. For a participant to be considered as a probability sample, he/she must be selected using a random selection. Probability sampling uses statistical theory to randomly select a small group of people (sample) from an existing large population and then predict that all their responses will match the overall population. The sample collected from Target respondents are users, Populations are infinitely, Sample size is 110. Both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics methods were used in the study for analysis purposes.

DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE BASIS OF AGE

TABLE- 6.1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
21-30 yrs	44	40.0	40.0	40.0
31-40 yrs	29	26.0	26.0	66.0
40-50 yrs	37	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

EXHIBIT-6.1 AGE GROUP

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that 40% of the respondents belong to the age group of 21-30 years, 26% of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years and 34% of the respondents belong to the age group of 41 years and above.

DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE BASIS OF GENDER

TABLE- 6.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	92	84.0	84.0	84.0
Female	18	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

EXHIBIT- 6.2 GENDER

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that 84% of the respondents male and 16% of the respondents female.

DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE BASIS OF EXPERIENCE

TABLE- 6.3 Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2 to 5 years	40	36.0	36.0	36.0
6 to 10 years	66	60.0	60.0	96.0
11 to 15 years	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

EXHIBIT- 6.3 EXPERIENCE

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that 36% of the respondents belong to 2 to 5 years of experience, 60% of the respondents belong to 6 – 10 years of experience and 4% of the respondents belong to 11 to 15 years & above of experience.

ONE-WAY ANOVA

is a statistical technique used to compare means across multiple groups. It’s commonly used when you have one independent variable (also known as a factor) with more than two levels , and you want to determine if there are any significant differences in the means of a dependent variable among those levels.

Null hypothesis (Ho):

There is a significance difference between the New Employee Organization.

Alternate hypothesis (H1):

There is no significance difference between the New Employee Organization.

ANOVA

NEW EMPLOYEE ORGANIZATION

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	28.587	3	9.529	141.639	.000
Within Groups	7.131	106	.067		
Total	35.718	109			

INFERENCE:

there is no significance difference between the New Employee Organization. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis

FINDINGS

- 41% of the respondents agrees that organization’s induction provides an understanding of the company’s culture, structure, products and clients
- 42% of the respondents feel that induction includes setting out work objectives department and company goals

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- 54% of the respondents feel that induction process enable the newcomers to meet colleagues with whom they will be working in the future.
- 55% of the respondents feel that the employee orientation is not effective in the employment integration
- 35% of the respondents strongly agree that induction provides the newcomer with skills and knowledge to do their duties well

SUGGESTIONS

- Top management must allow the managers to know about the organizations future plans which help them develop their new employees by giving them the proper training in the induction program and prepare them for future development of the organization.
- Employees of the organization should be given more freedom in performing their work and also by giving their own innovative ideas for the upcoming project that is undertaken by the organization.
- The induction training program should be very effective and efficient for the employees. The employee's smart working should be appreciated and recognized for their contribution and efforts taken by them.

CONCLUSION

Induction training is very essential for any company because it helps an individual/new recruit to grow within a company and motivates him/her. It inculcates in the employee, more confidence to progress. It is during induction that a new recruit gets to know about the organization's employment philosophy, physical work environment, employee's rights, employee's responsibilities, organization, culture and values along with key business processes. Employee Induction should last more than one day, usually 2-5 days. Employee induction should always start with HR's welcome from the appointed host from that department, who is responsible to guide newcomer through department in order to introduce him to the other. This dedicated HR person is not spending all time following newcomer through departments, but will be at disposal, to escort him/her to the next department during the Employee induction.

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